

WAYS OF GROWING ROSE AND NEW VARIETIES

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Annotation: Rose (Rosa) is a common name given by the people to several species of the rhododendron family that are cultivated as ornamental plants. The wild species of this family are popularly known by the names of rana, namatak, chirgy agayni and itburun. Widespread in Asia, Europe, America.

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There are 250 species of roses on Earth, more than 25 thousand varieties. 19 species, more than 600 varieties are grown in Uzbekistan. These varieties differ in their features, such as the size of the flower, color, smell, location on the stem, flowering period, and whether the stem is upright or compact; The varieties that bloom continuously or repeatedly throughout the season and grow together with the stem are more planted. The rose is mainly propagated by grafting, cuttings and cuttings.

In propagation by grafting, the seeds extracted from the fruits of namatak harvested in July are stored in a moist place and are sown in the open field in late November - early December. After the seed has germinated, next year April - August. it is mowed 4-5 times, watered 8-10 times; in August-September, buds of the Rose variety are grafted onto the vine. Next year, in early spring, the graft is cut from the top of the bud attached to it, and the ticket that binds the graft is released. During the summer, the branches are plucked 1-2 times, after the grafted flower grows 15-20 cm, it is not allowed to grow tall and bloom prematurely.

For this, the tip of the grafted flower is cut, and the side branches are shortened from time to time. Roses can be propagated from cuttings by treating them with special growth activators.

Rose seedlings are planted in flower beds in autumn and spring. The soil of the flower garden is preliminarily softened to a depth of 30-35 cm, 5-10 kg of manure is added to 1 m² of land. Seedlings are planted in 70 x 70 cm spacing. The width of the seedling pit is 30-40 cm, and the depth is 40-50 cm. During the summer, the flower bed is watered up to 20 times, watered up to 6 times, fed 2 times (at the expense of 30 g of saltpeter and 45 g of ammonium sulfate per 1 m² of land), treated with sulfur powder against powdery mildew, and kept free of weeds. In late autumn, the branches are cut, leaving 1-2 buds.

Gulkand and jam are made from the petals of some varieties. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the rose blooms in the open ground from April to the end of November, in greenhouses it is possible to get flowers all year round. In France, Bulgaria, Turkey, Italy and other countries, valuable essential oil is extracted from some species (damask, French, etc.). The rose is sewn in the national Iraqi style in embroidery (including cap-making), carved in jewelry (on the face of a bracelet), copper (decoration of copper dishes) and in other ways.

Origin and characteristics of roses.

Plants known as roses or roses are a series of shrubs of the genus *Rosa*, usually with thorns. There are about 100 species, growing in Asia, North America, Europe and Northwest Africa, but most of them are found on the Asian continent. More than 30,000 varieties of these varieties have been created, and new ones appear every year. They are characterized by bushes or climbers that can grow from 10 centimeters to 20 meters in height. depending on the type or variety. The stem is semi-woody, protected by thick sharp thorns. These outgrowths consist of 5 to 9 leaflets or pinnae, serrated edges and green, deciduous or perennial.

Flower sizes from 2 to 10 centimeters in diameter are good. Its leaves can be very different colors: red, white, yellow, pink or even two-colored (for example, red with white spots). The fruit is called rose hip, consists of many small fruits and has a red color when ripe.

New varieties of roses.

Crimson Glory - For a classic, crimson rose, it's hard to beat 'Crimson Glory,' a climbing rose that you can train on a trellis or trellis.

Cherry Parfait - This is a two-toned rose that looks mostly red, especially from a distance. Up close, you can see that the base of each leaf is actually white. 'Cherry Parfait' is a type of Meiland rose.

Falstaff - 'Falstaff' is a double flower with a deep purplish red color.

Thomas Becket - This variety produces pale red to scarlet flowers with a bushy habit.

Modern Fireglow - For something more orange, try this variety with double flowers.

Walko - For a gorgeous red flower that also has a scent, try 'Walko'.

Hot Cocoa - This is a really rare variety of rose with a reddish-brown color. The aroma is fruity and spicy. This variety is a type of floribunda.

Munstead Wood - The buds of this variety are pale red, but after the flowers open, they turn a deep, beautiful burgundy with a classic, rose fragrance.

Stars Eternal Stripes - This American patriot variety impresses with white and red striped flowers.

Rose is the national flower of USA, Iran and England. Natural rose oil is one of the most expensive oils in the world. It is valued more than gold and platinum. You need three tons of rose petals to make one kilogram of rose oil. Valentine's Day is the day when most roses are sold in the world. On this day - about 3 million roses are bought. A person who regularly breathes the scent of roses will be sincere and calm. The fragrant incense smoke of flowers is burned to lift the mood.

Shakespeare mentioned roses more than 50 times in his works. One of the unusual varieties of the flower is named in his honor. The smallest rose in the world ("S" variety) is the size of a grain of rice. The oldest rose in the world grows in Hildesheim Cathedral in Germany. The rose bush reaches the roof of the building.

This rose is about 1000 years old. Damaged during the war, but saved by growing from the roots. Wild rose berries contain more vitamin C than lemons.

Their juice is an effective remedy for health. In Russia, a wonderful flower was seen in the 16th century. Peter I and Catherine II started to decorate the gardens with rose bushes. 10. There are many varieties of Chameleon roses in Japan. In the morning, the leaves of this rose are bright red, and in the evening - white.

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